

Relationship Between Professional Development and Teachers' Attitude to Work in Public Secondary Schools in Ikom Education Zone, Cross River State

Dr. (Mrs) Nkechi C. MARCHIE¹ & Dr. Goodfriday Kunuosowa NTUNO²

¹Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education,
University of Benin

²Department of Educational Foundations and Curriculum
Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria

¹nkechi.marchie@uniben.edu.

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Abstract

The study investigated the relationship between professional development and teachers' attitude to work in public secondary schools in Ikom Education zone of Cross River State. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. Correlation research survey was adopted for the study with a population that consisted of 1,494 teachers in Ikom education zone. A sample of 329 teachers from all public secondary schools in Ikom education zone was drawn using purposive and accidental techniques. The two instruments used for the collection of data were questionnaires titled, "Professional Development Questionnaire (PDQ) and Teachers' Attitude to Work Questionnaire (TAWQ). The two instruments were made on a four-point rating scale of Strongly Agreed, Agreed, Disagreed and Strongly Disagreed, and were scored 4,3,2 and 1 respectively. Data was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and multiple regression in line with the research variables at p-value of 0.05 level of significance. Findings of the study revealed that, there is a significant relationship between teachers' participation in in-service training and teachers' attitude to work. It was also established that teachers' participation in conferences is significantly related to attitude to work in public secondary schools in Ikom Education zone of Cross River State. The study concluded that professional development programmes has a strong relationship with teachers' attitude to work in public secondary schools in Ikom Education zone. The study recommended that school administrators and state Ministry of Education should make it mandatory for teachers to participate in all in-service training organized by state Ministry of Education and non-governmental organizations. Also, school leaders and non-governmental organizations should quarterly organize conferences for teachers to improve their attitude to their work.

Keywords: Professional development, teachers' attitude, Work, secondary schools

Introduction

One of the ultimate intentions of establishing secondary education is to prepare individual citizens to live useful in the society and to provide junior secondary school leavers the opportunity to further their education (Ntuno, et'al., 2021). This suggest that the acquisition of secondary education is a necessary basic condition to unveil skills and creative thinking for wealth creation which is a sure path to successful living and achievement of educational goals by learners.

However, this cannot be achieved when there are pronounced exhibitions of negative attitudes of teachers towards their work which to a large extent has affected the students' motivation, engagement, and overall academic performance. Considering the crucial role of a teacher in the academic achievement and overall development of their pupils, it is therefore imperative for teachers to possess desired qualities like command on the subject, moral and mental fitness, devotion to the profession and appropriate skill to perform his or her duties for the achievement of the coveted objectives.

Unfortunately the expected qualities of trained and professional teachers seems not demonstrated by most teachers in Ikom Education Zone of Cross River State. Common observation has revealed that many teachers demonstrate a high level of futile attitude in terms of punctuality, engaging in conflict with school administrators, ineffective notes of lesson writing, high degree of absenteeism and other disciplinary attitudes to work (Arop, et'al., 2018). This has triggered serious concern by the researcher, government and other stakeholders. Thus, such negative attitudes demonstrated by teachers are not only unprofessional, unethical, and inimical but has hindered the realizations of teaching profession and educational goals. More so, the negative attitudes of the teachers towards their students have created adverse impact on the students' academic performance, learning, emotion and lifestyle. In other words, when positive attitudes are portrayed by well-trained and professional teachers towards the students, the result produces positive outcomes. Little wonder, Ntuno. et'al., (2024), opined that the productivity of any system is predicated on the quality of training given to the staff. This informed the fact that, the teacher's performance and effective service delivery in school depends to a large extend on the teacher's professional development.

Teacher's professional development according to Health (2018) is a systematic attempt to harmonize individuals' interests and wishes, and carefully assessed requirements of the organization in attaining new skills and knowledge, gaining increasing levels of competence, and growing professionally for effective performance. This entails that professional development helps to enhance teacher's skills, knowledge and ability on effective performance for the achievement of set goals in school. It further explains that professional development improve the quality of teaching and learning for effective service delivery in a school system. This study therefore, focused on in-service training and conference programmes, and teachers' attitudes to work.

In-service training is a programme that improve the school staff capacity and intellectual development. According to Ntuno, et'al., (2024) in-service training programme is a comprehensible set of activities that helps in broadening the knowledge, attitudes, and skills of school staff for effective service delivery. In the same vein, Ogunbodede (2016) posited that in-service training is a kind of education which is done to help the individuals in organization to acquire knowledge, skills and attitudes in their jobs. This entails that in-service training is on the job or off-the job training that help to facilitate effective learning process in school. It further implies that in-service is a professional training aimed at broadening staff intellectual knowledge on skills for continuous professional growth.

The views above are supported by Utopia and Ikpe (2012) study on the influence of administration of in-service training and teachers' attitude to work in private secondary schools in

Cross River State of Nigeria. The sample comprised 800 teachers, randomly selected from a population of 2946 teachers. The null hypothesis that guided the study was tested with a set of questionnaire. Independent t-test statistical tool used to analyze the data yielded the finding that administration of in-service training programme significantly influences teachers' attitude to work in private secondary schools. On the basis of the above finding, it was recommended among other things that systematic and regular in-service training courses should be organized by the proprietors of private secondary schools. These training courses would up-date, motivate and enhance teachers teaching skills for effective performance. Job enrichment in a school system is a way of increasing the responsibilities of staff and this may have positive influence on their attitude to work at the new position if they have the prerequisite skill to function in that capacity. Hence, the findings of the author also applies to job improvement which can be secured through in-service training, and which can boost staffs ego to put in their best in the school system.

Another study was conducted by Fejoh and Faniran (2016) on the impact of in-service training and staff development on workers' job performance and optimal productivity in public secondary schools in Osun State, Nigeria. The study used the ex-post-facto research design. The instrument for data collection was the Likert type questionnaire which was administered to a sample of 152 respondents while 134 questionnaires were returned. Data generated were analyzed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Multiple Regression Analysis. The findings showed that in-service training and staff development had insignificant combined effects but significant relative effects on workers' optimal job productivity. The study therefore recommended that schools should design proper and functioning in-service training and staff development programmes for their workers to boost their morale, enhance their performance and in addition ensure that workers training are conducted frequently to ensure they cope with changing technological environment and organizational climate in schools.

Based on the result from the study of Utopia and Ikpe (2012), and Fejoh and Faniran (2016) it was evident that professional development helps to enhance teacher's skills, knowledge ability and effective performance for the achievement of set goals in school. This is maintained by Iwuagwu and Aiwuyo (2017) who asserted that when teachers are offered in-service training, they acquire new and improved skills as well as knowledge that will enable them perform better thereby enhancing their productivity.

Another training programme that elicits human capacity and intellectual development of teachers is attendance of conferences. According to Ntuno, et'al., (2024) staff development especially conferences helps to improve teachers teaching strategies, techniques and skills that are required for effective service delivery. This implies that staff development through conferences, offer one of the best ways of enhancing teaching and learning process.

Conference attendance according to Eze (2016) affords the teachers the opportunity of learning about professional issues and brainstorm with colleagues to keep abreast of the latest trend. Ntuno, et'al., (2024) highlighted that conference attendance improve staff networking value, strengthens team work, enhances current and future challenges in the teaching profession. This buttressed the fact that conference attendance improves the staff professional capacity and

provides valuable opportunities for the staff to keep current on various tools necessary to perform day- to- day job responsibilities in the secondary schools.

The views above are maintained by a study that was carried out by Udida, et'al., (2015) on staff development opportunities and teacher's effectiveness in nursery schools in Cross River State, Nigeria. A survey design was adopted for the study. A sample of two hundred (200) teachers was sampled from a population of 1,258 primary schools in the study area. Questionnaire was used to eliciting information from the respondents. Mean, standard deviation and Pearson product moment correlation statistics was used for data description and analysis. The result of the analysis revealed a significant positive relationship between conference attendance and teacher's effectiveness in the study area. It was generally concluded that conference participation enhances teacher's effectiveness.

Another study was carried out by Oviawe (2016) on "Teachers' Effectiveness as Correlates of Students' Academic Achievement in Basic Technology in Nigeria". The study investigated the relationship between teachers' effectiveness and students' academic achievement in Basic Technology in Edo State Model secondary schools, Nigeria using descriptive survey research design. The instruments used to elicit information for the study were Teachers' Effectiveness Rating Scale (TERS) and Basic Technology Achievement Test (BTAT). Simple percentage, t-test and ANOVA were the statistical tools used in the analysis of data. The findings revealed that Basics Technology Teachers' effectiveness had influence on student's achievement due to teachers' training and re-training programmes through attendance of conferences. This further confirmed that conference attendance advances the teachers' professional capability and provides valuable opportunities for the teachers to be abreast with the contemporary trend for the achievement of set goals in the school system. It was based on the views above the researcher sought to examine the relationship between professional development and teachers' attitude to work in Public Secondary Schools in Ikom Education Zone, Cross River State.

Statement of the problem

Researchers and personal experience have shown that some teachers working in public secondary schools in Ikom Education Zone, Cross River State seems to be relenting in taking their primary assignment of teaching seriously, instead they display poor attitude to work such as absenteeism, non-writing of lesson note, using lessons hours for other businesses and some come to school very late when they are supposed to be in the first period of lesson. Others take permission to be off from duty thereby leaving the students to wander about leading to poor academic performance of the students.

More so, the absence of regular in-service training and sponsorship of conferences by school administrators and Ministry of Education for the professional development of teachers in public secondary schools in Ikom zone of Cross River State. Undeniably, without professional development in schools, teachers will be stock with old method of teaching, lack new teaching strategies; thereby making teaching boring and unsatisfactory, resulting to poor performance and unproductivity in general school system. This study therefore seeks to investigate the relationship

between professional development and teachers' attitude to work in public secondary schools in Ikom Education Zone, Cross River State

Objectives of the study

The study was set to:

1. Investigate the relationship between teacher's participation in in-service training and teachers' attitude to work in public secondary schools.
2. Examine the relationship between teacher's participation in conferences and their attitude to work in public secondary schools.

Research questions

The study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the relationship between teachers' participation in in-service training and their attitude to work in public secondary schools?
2. What is the relationship between teachers' participation in conferences and their attitude to work in public secondary schools in Ikom Education Zone?

Methodology

The research design for this study was correlation research survey design. The population of the study was 1,494 teachers in all the public secondary Schools in Ikom Education Zone. The sample of the study represented twenty-two percent (22%) of the population and was derived from Yamane, Taro (1967) optimal allocation sample size determination technique and strategy. Based on the statistics made available by the Cross River State Secondary Education Board (CRSSEB) 2023, there were a total of 111 public secondary schools in five Local Government Areas; namely, Abi, Boki, Etung, Ikom, Obubra and Yakur comprises of Ikom Education Zone, Cross River State. The study adopted purposive and accidental techniques to get the sample size of 329 drawn from all the public secondary schools in Ikom education zone. The researchers used their judgment and empirical knowledge to select teachers in the public secondary schools in Ikom zone of Cross River State.

Accordingly, the instruments used for data collection was questionnaire and the questionnaires for data collection was a 20-items questionnaire tagged "Professional Development Questionnaire (PDQ) and a 10 items questionnaire (TAWQ). The instruments were validated by two Measurement and Evaluation experts from Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. Reliability of the instruments were determined using Cronbach alpha reliability co-efficient with the reliability index of PDQ estimated as 0.80 and that of TAWQ estimated as 0.84. The instruments were administered by the researchers with the aid of two trained Research Assistants and all the 329 copies of questionnaires administered were retrieved indicating 100% retrieval rate. Data was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and multiple regression in line with the research variables at p-value of 0.05 level of significance. Major findings were discussed based on the results on the data analyzed.

Table 1. Sample of the Study.

S/N	Local Govt. Area	No. of schools	No of teachers	No. of teachers selected (22%)
1	Abi	13	151	33
2	Boki	30	231	51
3	Etung	12	120	26
4	Ikom	20	385	85
5	Obubra	19	180	40
6	Yakurr	17	427	94
Total		111	1,494	329

The breakdown of the sample of the study from each Local Government Areas in table 1 shows the 329 teachers representing 22% of the population of teachers in public secondary schools in Ikom Education Zone of Cross River State.

Research Question One: What is the relationship between teachers’ participation in in-service training and their attitude to work in public secondary schools?

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis of the relationship between teachers’ participation in in-service training and teachers’ attitude to work (N= 329)

Variables	N	x	Sd	r	df	p-value
Teachers’ participation in in-service training	329	13.10	1.43	.519*	327	.000
Teachers’ attitude to work	329	26.04	2.78			

*Significant at .05, df = 327.

Table 2 shows that teachers’ participation in in-service training has a positive relationship with teachers’ attitude to work as $r = .519$. Also, when this was tested at 0.05 significance, ($r = .519, P = 0.000 < 0.05$), it shows that this has a positive significant relationship. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship between teachers’ participation in in-service training and teachers’ attitude to work in Ikom Education Zone of Cross River State is therefore rejected. This result means that as the teachers’ participation in in-service training increases, their attitude to work also improves and vice versa.

Research Question Two: What is the relationship between teachers’ participation in conferences and their attitude to work in public secondary schools in Ikom Education Zone?

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis of the relationship between teachers’ participation in conferences and teachers’ attitude to work.

Variables	N	x	Sd	r	df	p-value
Teachers’ participation in conferences	329	12.40	1.49	.522*	327	.000
Teachers’ attitude to work	329	26.04	2.78			

*Significant at .05, $df = 327$.

Table 3 shows that teachers' participation in conferences has a positive relationship with teachers' attitude to work as $r = .522$. Also, when this was tested at 0.05 significance, ($r = .522$, $P = 0.000 < 0.05$), it shows that this has a positive significant relationship. The null hypothesis is of no significant relationship between teachers' participation in conferences and teachers' attitude to work in Ikom Education Zone of Cross River State is therefore rejected. This means that as the teachers' participation in conference increases, the teachers' attitude to work also improves. However, when teachers' participation in conferences decreases, their attitude to work also decreases.

Discussion of findings

The study was able to establish that there is a significant relationship between teachers' participation in in-service training and teachers' attitude to work in public secondary schools in Ikom Education Zone. This further reveal that when teachers actively participate in in-service training, they advance in their insights and teaching strategies, develop a deeper understanding of their subject matter and overall performance in the achievement of set goals. This is in agreement with Udofia and Ikpe (2012) findings on their investigation of the influence of administration of in-service training and teachers' attitude to work in private secondary schools in Cross River State of Nigeria, that administration of in-service training programme significantly influences teachers' attitude to work in private secondary schools. This is also in conformity with the finding of Fejoh and Faniran (2016) on their study on the impact of in-service training and staff development on workers' job performance and optimal productivity in public secondary schools in Osun State, Nigeria. The study also showed that in-service training and staff development had insignificant combined effects on workers' optimal job productivity.

The above revelations has clearly divulge to that the fact that teachers' capacity and intellectual development can be advanced if in-service training programmes are taken into considerations in public secondary schools. This is also in agreement with the views of Ntuno, Ikwuobe and Yusuf (2024) that in-service training programme is a comprehensible set of activities that helps in broadening the knowledge, attitudes, and skills of school staff for effective service delivery.

Moreover, the study established that there is a significant relationship between teachers' participation in conference and teachers' attitude to work in public secondary schools in Ikom Education Zone. This implies that conferences provide opportunities for teachers to engage in professional development, inform on new teaching techniques, and exchange ideas with colleagues. These experiences can enhance their knowledge, skills, and motivation, which may positively influence their attitudes towards work. This views are in line with the findings of Udida, Okpa and Wonah (2015) on their study on staff development opportunities and teacher's effectiveness in nursery schools in Cross River State, Nigeria. The result of the analysis revealed that there is a positive relationship between conference attendance and teacher's effectiveness in school. This implies that staff development through conferences, offer one of the best ways of enhancing teaching and learning process. It further entails that conference attendance elicits human

capacity and intellectual development of teachers. This views are upheld by Ntuno, Ikwuobe and Yusuf (2024) that staff development especially conferences helps to improve teachers teaching strategies, techniques and skills that are required for effective service delivery.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that professional development programmes offer teachers the acquisition of new and improved skills as well as knowledge that will enable them perform better thereby enhancing their productivity in school system especially teachers in public secondary schools in Ikom Education Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Recommendation

1. The study recommend that school leaders and state Ministry of Education should make it mandatory for teachers to participate in all in-service training organized by state ministry of education and non-governmental organizations
2. Also, School administrators and non-governmental organizations should help in organizing conferences for teachers quarterly to improve their attitude to their work.

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